

CAMELINA SATIVA PROTOCOL FOR INTRODUCTION AS A COVER CROP FOR MARGINAL LAND IN SPAIN

INTRODUCTION

Camelina is a suitable winter intermediate crop for marginal lands typically characterized by low productivity, poor soil quality, limited rainfall, extreme temperatures, steep slopes, or susceptibility to erosion, thus presenting challenges to income generation for farmers. The present protocol, optimized within the UNTWIST project through three years of field experiments in Castilla la Mancha (Spain), addresses the introduction of camelina as intermediate crop following winter cereals and/or winter legumes.

FACTS

- **Common names:** Camelina, Leindotter, Gold of Pleasure, False Flax.
- **Scientific name:** *Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz
Family: Brassicaceae or Cruciferae.
- **Drought-resistant oil crop** with a yield potential of 2.5 t/ha.
- **Plant height:** 60 to 120 cm.
- **Pollinator friendly species.**
- **1000-seed weight:** 0.8 - 1.6 g.

ADVANTAGES

- **Conventional machinery for winter cereals.**
- **Easy implementation & low-input crop.**
- **Drought & frost tolerant.**
- **Catch crop.**
- **Pest & disease tolerant.**
- **Pivoting root** - soil structure improver.
- **Different cycle length varieties** are available.
- **Excellent crop in rotation with cereals.**

AGRONOMIC PROTOCOL KEY POINTS

PLOTS

Avoid easily waterlogged soils, with crust formation and pH less than 5.5 and greater than 8.5.

SOWING

Shallow sowing (≈ 1 cm) in rows (12.5 -15 cm distance) on a plot without weeds or straw.

NUTRIENTS

Guarantee minimum nitrogen availability including soil N (60 kg N/ha).

HERBICIDES

Check residual herbicides (mainly ALS & PDS).

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Sowing date, sowing rate and strategy as well as nitrogen fertilization rate was optimized in 3-year field trials within the **UNTWIST project**. The other parts of the protocol are based on previous experience with the crop and other projects and research work.

STAGES IN CAMELINA PRODUCTION

Photographs provided by Camelina Company.